

INTERACTION OF THIONYL CHLORIDE AND AROMATIC HYDROXY
KETONES IN PRESENCE OF FINELY DIVIDED COPPER. PART VIII.
PRÉPARATION OF 3:3'-DIBUTYRYL-4:6-4':6'-TETRAHYDROXY-
DIPHENYL THIOETHER AND ITS DERIVATIVES
FROM RESBUTYROPHENONE

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Preparation of 3:3'-dibutyryl-4:6-4':6'-tetrahydroxydiphenyl thioether and its tetra-acetoxy, di-methoxy and tetramethoxy derivatives is described. Nitration and bromination as well as 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone derivative of the tetrahydroxy thioether are also described.

Present work is the continuation of the work under publication. The reaction was carried out in presence of dry chloroform at room temperature, affording the thioether (I). Its constitution was arrived at by the formation of a nitroresbutyrophenone by the action of nitric acid on it below 10°. It is found to be different from authentic 3-nitroresbutyrophenone (2:4-dihydroxy-3-nitrobutyrophenone), prepared from 2-nitroresorcinol by Friedel and Crafts' reaction, and therefore it is given the constitution 2:4-dihydroxy-5-nitrobutyrophenone. This constitution has further been confirmed by its identity with the nitration product of resbutyrophenone. This shows that the two nuclei are linked through sulphur atoms in the position *para* to -OH group and *meta* to -COC₂H₅ group, and hence, the thioether is 3:3'-dibutyryl-4:6-4':6'-tetrahydroxy-diphenyl thioether (I).

Bromination of the thioether (I) with bromine, slightly more than two molecules for one of (I) in acetic acid, furnishes the dibromo-thioether (V), which constitution is supported by the formation of 2:4-dihydroxy-3-bromo-5-nitrobutyrophenone (VI) by the action of nitric acid on it, as proved by its mixed melting point with a genuine specimen prepared by bromination of 2:4-dihydroxy-5-nitrobutyrophenone in acetic acid medium.

With excess of liquid bromine, 2:4:6-tribromoresorcinol is obtained, showing that bromine oxidises the ketonic group to -COOH group which loses carbon dioxide, and the resulting resorcinol is brominated. Tetra-acetoxy (II), dimethoxy² (III) and tetramethoxy (IV) derivatives and 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazones of (I) have been prepared. The thioether (III) is also obtained from 4-methoxy-2-hydroxybutyrophenone by the action of thionyl chloride in presence of copper as well as by the action of sulphur monochloride and of sulphur dichloride.

Thioether (I) is also obtained from resbutyrophenone by the action of sulphur monochloride as well as of sulphur dichloride in ethereal solution.

EXPERIMENTAL

3:3'-Dibutyryl-4:6-4':6'-tetrahydroxydiphenyl Thioether (I).—Thionyl chloride (12 c.c.) was added to the ice-cooled solution of resbutyrophenone (14.5 g.) in dry

chloroform (80 c.c.). Copper powder (8 g.) was then added in small lots (over 1 hour). The reaction mixture was left overnight at room temperature and then filtered and the residue washed with chloroform. A dark brown semi-solid remained after removal of the chloroform (room temperature). It was first washed with petroleum ether (b.p. 40°-60°) and then treated with benzene when it solidified. It was finally crystallised from dilute alcohol in colorless needles, m.p. 170-71°, yield 5 g. (Found: C, 61.6; H, 6.0; S, 8.2. $C_{20}H_{22}O_6S$ requires C, 61.5; H, 5.6; S, 8.2 per cent).

It is easily soluble in alcohol, acetone and chloroform and sparingly so in benzene, and insoluble in petroleum ether. It develops a red coloration with alcoholic ferric chloride and is soluble in dilute alkali with a yellow colour.

The same thioether was also formed when resbutyrophenone (3.6 g.), dissolved in dry ether (50 c.c.) and cooled in ice, was treated with (i) sulphur monochloride (1 c.c.) or (ii) sulphur dichloride (1.5 c.c.), and the reaction was allowed to proceed for 1 hour at room temperature in the first case, and for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour in the second case.

In the first case the pasty mass, obtained after removal of the ether, was first shaken with petroleum ether and then extracted with alcohol. The solid obtained after removal of alcohol was washed with benzene and then crystallised from dilute alcohol in needles, m.p. 170-71°, yield 0.5 g.

In the second case the pasty mass, obtained after removal of the ether, was boiled with water and then first crystallised from acetic acid and finally from dilute alcohol, m.p. 170-71°, yield 0.5 g.

Tetra-acetoxy Derivative, (I) [II] was prepared by acetylating (I) with acetic anhydride in presence of pyridine. It was first crystallised from dilute alcohol and finally from petroleum ether, m.p. 98-99°. (Found: S, 5.6. $C_{22}H_{20}O_{10}S$ requires S, 5.7 per cent).

3:3'-Dibutyl-4:4'-dihydroxy-6:6'-dimethoxydiphenyl thioether (III) was obtained by methylating (I, 0.5 g.) with dimethyl sulphate (0.3 c.c.) in dry acetone medium (20 c.c.) in presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate (1 g.) by refluxing the mixture on a water-bath for 10 hours. The solid obtained from acetone was crystallised from alcohol in white needles, m.p. 155-56°. (Found: S, 7.6. $C_{22}H_{26}O_6S$ requires S, 7.7 per cent). It shows a bluish green coloration with alcoholic ferric chloride and is soluble in dilute alkali with a yellow colour.

The same substance was also obtained when copper powder (2 g.) was gradually added (over 1 hour) to a cooled solution of 2-hydroxy-4-methoxybutyrophenone (4 g.) in dry chloroform (20 c.c.) and thionyl chloride (3 c.c.). Chloroform was filtered next day and the pasty mass, left after removal of the chloroform (at room temperature), was first washed with petroleum ether and then boiled with water. The semi-solid mass was first crystallised from acetic acid and then from dilute alcohol in colorless needles, m.p. 155-56°.

It was also obtained by the action of (i) sulphur monochloride (1 c.c.) or (ii) sulphur dichloride (1.5 c.c.) on ice-cooled dry ethereal solution of 2-hydroxy-4-methoxybutyrophenone (4 g. in 50 c.c.) and working up in the same way as in the case of thionyl chloride reaction.

Tetramethoxy derivative of (I) [IV] was prepared by methylating (I) with excess of dimethyl sulphate in acetone medium in presence of 4% KOH solution by heating it in a water-bath for 1 hour. The white solid separating was crystallised from alcohol in needles, m.p. 165-66°. (Found: S, 7.0. $C_{22}H_{20}O_8S$ requires S, 7.2 per cent).

2:4-Dinitrophenylhydrazone of the thioether (I) was obtained as red plates from acetic acid, m.p. 255-56° (decomp.). (Found: N, 14.9. $C_{12}H_{10}O_2N_2S$ requires N, 14.9 per cent).

2:4-Dihydroxy-5-nitrobutyrophenone.—The thioether (I, 1 g.) was gradually added to ice-cooled nitric acid (d 1.4, 10 c.c.). The reaction was allowed to proceed at that temperature for about 2 hours and then diluted with ice. The solid obtained was crystallised from dilute alcohol in shining yellow needles, m.p. 120-21°. (Found: N, 6.4. $C_{10}H_{11}O_5N$ requires N, 6.2 per cent) (mixed m.p. with the authentic specimen prepared by the action of nitric acid in presence of acetic acid on 2:4-dihydroxybutyrophenone).

3:3'-Dibutyl-4:6:4':6'-tetrahydroxy-5:5'-dibromodiphenyl Thioether (V).—A solution of bromine in acetic acid (32 c.c. of 10% solution, w/v) was added to the hot solution of the thioether (I, 3.5 g.) in acetic acid (20 c.c.). A white bromo derivative soon separated which was crystallised from acetic acid in colorless needles, m.p. 216-17°, yield 2.5 g. (Found: Br, 29.0. $C_{20}H_{20}O_8Br_2S$ requires Br, 29.2 per cent).

2:4:6-Tribromoresorcinol.—Liquid bromine (5 c.c.) was added to the thioether (1 g.) when it went into solution. The reaction was allowed to proceed overnight. The liquid was then diluted and the solid separating was washed with sodium bisulphite and crystallised from hot water, m.p. 110-11°. No lowering in melting point was observed when mixed with a genuine specimen prepared from resorcinol according to Benedikt (Monatsh., 1883, 4, 227).

2:4-Dihydroxy-3-bromo-5-nitrobutyrophenone (VI).—The thioether (V, 1 g.) was suspended in acetic acid (10 c.c.), and nitric acid (d 1.4, 5 c.c.) was added to it and warmed on a boiling water-bath until a clear solution was formed. It was then poured over ice and the solid obtained was crystallised from dilute alcohol in pale yellow needles, m.p. 120-21°. (Found: Br, 26.2. $C_{10}H_{10}O_5NBr$ requires Br, 26.3 per cent).

It showed no lowering in melting point with the genuine specimen prepared by brominating 5-nitroresorcinol in acetic acid medium.